

IMPACT OF PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA ON FARMER'S INCOME STABILITY IN DHARASHIV DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA.

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the progress of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in the Dharashiv district of Maharashtra. The focus is on assessing its impact on income stability for various crops while identifying the weaknesses in its implementation. Multistage purposive sampling technique was used for selection of district, talukas, villages & sample farmers. Involving 12 villages across four talukas Umerga, Kallamb, Tuljapur, and Dharashiv. The selection of these villages allows for a comprehensive understanding of the PMFBY's impact in different local contexts. The research employed random sampling to select 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers. Primary data were collected through a pre-tested schedule, ensuring the reliability of the information gathered. Additionally, secondary data were obtained from governmental reports and publications from insurance companies, providing a broader context for the findings. The analysis revealed a minimal growth rate of just 1 per cent for both kharif and rabi insured farmers. However, PMFBY has shown a positive impact on income stability, evidenced by a decrease in income variability and an increase in the income index from 0.69 to 0.80. Despite these benefits, several challenges persist, including delayed claim payments, low awareness of the scheme, and a shortage of trained professionals. Farmers highlighted the need for quicker claim settlements, increased compensation rates, and greater transparency in the claims process. In conclusion, while the PMFBY has the potential to enhance income stability for farmers, its effectiveness is significantly hindered by various implementation challenges. To improve the scheme's impact and ensure broader participation, it is crucial to address these weaknesses through targeted interventions and enhanced engagement with farmers.

Keywords: Growth rate, Insured farmers, Income stability, Transparency, Awareness, PMFBY, Random sampling, Income index.

Introduction

Crop insurance serves as a crucial financial safeguard for farmers and agricultural producers, protecting them against unforeseen events that can significantly impact crop yields. This insurance type encompasses a variety of risks, including natural disasters such as droughts and floods, severe weather conditions like hail or frost, and damage caused by pests and diseases. By compensating farmers when actual crop yields fall below predetermined levels, crop insurance mitigates the financial uncertainties inherent in farming. In India, agriculture's vulnerability to such disasters is compounded by epidemics and man-made crises, including fires, counterfeit seeds, and market price crashes. The consequences of these events can drastically affect farmers' productivity and income, leading to serious social issues, including the alarming rate of farmer suicides. Therefore, crop insurance is vital for maintaining stability and resilience in agriculture, enabling farmers to recover from financial setbacks and invest in better practices and technologies.

The history of crop insurance in India dates back to 1920, when Mr. Chakravarti introduced a rain insurance scheme in Mysore State. This pioneering effort aimed to protect farmers from monsoon uncertainties, laying the groundwork for future initiatives. Despite its innovative approach, it remained largely unrecognized. After India's independence in 1947, discussions on crop insurance gained momentum, leading to several pilot schemes; however, financial constraints hindered their implementation. The 1972 experimental crop insurance scheme was also short-lived. The significant turning point came in 1979 with the introduction of the Pilot Crop Insurance Scheme (PCIS), which covered various crops for loanee farmers. This was followed by the Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS) in 1985, which aimed to extend coverage and provide subsidies for small and marginal farmers. Since then, various initiatives, including the National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS) in 1999 and the Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS) in 2003, have aimed to enhance financial protection for farmers against diverse risks. A landmark initiative, the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), was introduced in 2016, marking a significant advancement in India's crop insurance landscape. This scheme is one of the largest crop

insurance programs globally, designed to provide extensive risk cover to Indian farmers. It features a highly subsidized premium structure, allowing farmers to pay only a minimal percentage of the premium (2%) for kharif crops and (1.5%) for Rabi crops while the government covers the remaining costs. PMFBY has removed earlier premium capping, ensuring that farmers receive claims based on the full sum insured. Technological advancements, such as smartphone applications for data collection and remote sensing for crop assessment, aim to reduce delays in claim payments and enhance transparency. Despite these improvements, the scheme is still in its early stages, and comprehensive assessments of its efficacy are essential.

In the context of Dharashiv district in the Marathwada region, a study is underway to evaluate the progress of the PMFBY scheme. As of the Rabi season in 2023, the total number of farmers in Dharashiv stands at 3,04,792, with only 3,840 benefiting from the insurance, highlighting a substantial gap in coverage. During the kharif season, the number of farmers reaches 3,71,333, with a similar disparity between loanee and non-loanee farmers. The area insured in both seasons also reflects the underutilization of this vital safety net. The objectives of the study include analyzing the implementation of PMFBY, the role of insurance agencies, and the scheme's impact on income stability from various crops. www.pmfby.gov.in.

While PMFBY represents a significant step forward, it is not without limitations. Challenges such as insufficient compensation, administrative hurdles, and a lack of awareness among farmers persist. The effectiveness of the scheme can be enhanced by addressing these weaknesses and ensuring broader participation among farmers, particularly small and marginal ones. Continuous assessments of the scheme across diverse agro-climatic zones will be crucial for aligning premiums with fair actuarial standards, ensuring that the benefits of crop insurance are equitably distributed among farmers, and ultimately contributing to the sustainability and resilience of India's agricultural sector.

Objective

1. To study the progress of PMFBY in Dharashiv District of Maharashtra state.

2. To analysis the Impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers
3. To identify the weakness in implementation of PMFBY and suggestion suitable measures for its improvement

Materials And Methodology

Dharashiv district was purposively selected for the study due to its relevance in evaluating the progress of PMFBY. Within the district, four talukas Umerga, Kallamb, Tuljapur and Dharashiv, were chosen based on their performance under the scheme. From each taluka, three villages were selected, making a total of 12 villages, with the selection criteria being the progress of PMFBY implementation. In each village, 10 insured farmers and 10 non-insured farmers were randomly chosen, resulting in a sample size of 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers. Primary data were collected from these farmers using a pre-tested schedule during the *khari* season of 2023. To study the weaknesses in the implementation of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) and identify measures for its improvement Garrett's Technique is used.

Progress of PMFBY

The study was primarily based on secondary data. Information related to various aspects of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) was collected from multiple sources, including publications and reports from the Agriculture Insurance Company of India Limited, as well as official government websites. To assess the growth performance of PMFBY, compound annual growth rates (CAGR) were computed for key indicators such as the number of farmers covered under the scheme, the total area insured, reported claims, approved claims, the total claim amounts disbursed, and the number of farmers who benefited.

Growth of any economic variable signifies its past performance. The analysis of growth usually in economic studies to find out the trend of a particular variable over a period of time. It clearly indicates the performance of the variable under consideration and hence it can be very well used for making interpretation and to evolve policy decision. The progress of PMFBY in Dharashiv district were studied by estimating CAGR of number of farmer insured, area insured, reported claim, approved claim, total claim paid and total farmer benefitted for a period of 8 years (2016-17 to 2023-24). The CAGR was estimated by using following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a \cdot b^t \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated (Number of farmer insured / Area insured / Reported claim / Approved claim / Total claim paid / Total farmer benefitted)

t = Time variable

b = Regression coefficient

a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the equation.

$$\text{CGR } (r) = [\text{Antilog } (\text{log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots (3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Impact of PMFBY on income stability from various crop

Impact of PMFBY on stability of farm income were estimated by following method.

Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and interpret the data:

Mean (Average) Income:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum \text{income}}{N}$$

Where N is the number of observations.

Standard Deviation: Standard deviation is a measure of the extent to which the data is in reference to the mean. A low, or small, standard deviation implies that data is tightly assembled around the mean, whereas a high standard deviation implies that data is more spread out.

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X - \text{Mean})^2}{N}}$$

The standard deviation measures the amount of variation or dispersion from the average income.

Coefficient of Variation (CV): The Coefficient of Variation is a statistical measure of the relative variability or dispersion of a dataset in relation to its mean. It is commonly used to compare the degree of variation between different data sets, especially when the data are measured in different units or have different scales.

$$\text{CV} = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$$

This expresses the standard deviation as a percentage of the mean, indicating relative variability.

Income Index: A Measure of Income Stability

The Income Index was a metric used to assess the stability of income within a population or region. It was derived by normalizing the coefficient of variation (CV), a standard measure of relative variability, which allowed for the comparison of income distributions across different datasets. The index was calculated by subtracting the CV from 1, providing a standardized value between 0 and 1 that reflected the degree of income stability. Mathematically, the Income Index could be expressed as:

$$\text{Income index} = 1 - \text{CV}$$

Where: CV is the coefficient of variation, calculated as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean of the income distribution.

The interpretation of the Income Index is as follows:

Closer to 1: When the index approaches 1, it indicates that income within the population is relatively stable. A value of 1 signifies perfect income stability, where the standard deviation is minimal, and incomes are homogenous across the population.

Closer to 0: When the index nears 0, it reflects high income instability, suggesting that incomes vary greatly within the population. A value of 0 signifies perfect instability, where the income distribution is extremely unequal, characterized by a high degree of dispersion relative to the mean.

The Income Index, as a measure of income stability derived from the Coefficient of Variation (CV), provided a robust framework for analyzing differences in income stability between insured and non-insured farmers. This comparative analysis examined how insurance coverage influenced income stability, with the index revealing variations in financial outcomes between the two groups.

Garrett's Ranking Technique

It is a method used to rank various factors based on their perceived importance or severity, often applied in surveys where respondents rank their preferences or concerns.

Convert the ranks into Garrett scores using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Position} = \left(\frac{R_{ij} - 0.5}{N_j} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the *i*th factor by the *j*th individual

N_j = Number of factors ranked by the *j*th individual

Use Garrett's table to find the score corresponding to each percent position. The percentage position of each rank was converted into scores using Garrett's Table. For each factor, the scores from all individuals were summed up and then divided by the total number of farmers who provided scores. These average scores for each factor were then ranked in order, and conclusions were drawn based on these rankings.

Result And Discussion

To study the progress of PMFBY in India, Maharashtra and Dharshiv.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2012- 2023.

Table 1. presented the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for insured farmers from 2016 to 2023 reveals diverse trends across regions and cropping seasons. Nationally, the *kharif* season sees a decline of -7 per cent per annum, raising concerns about insurance outreach and participation barriers, while the *rabi* season shows modest growth of 2 per cent per annum, indicating some stability. In Maharashtra, the *kharif* season stands out with a significant CAGR of 20 per cent per annum, reflecting successful policies that have boosted insurance uptake. However, the *rabi* season shows stagnation, highlighting the need for ongoing efforts to enhance participation. Dharashiv shows minimal growth of 1 per cent per annum for both seasons, likely due to limited access to resources. These findings emphasize disparities in insurance adoption and the need for targeted strategies to strengthen farmer resilience against agricultural risks.

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Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of area insured under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Table 2. presented the analysis of the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of insured farmers from 2016 to 2023 reveals significant trends in agricultural insurance across India. Nationally, the CAGR for both *kharif* and *rabi* seasons stands at 1 per cent per annum, indicating stagnation in insurance adoption, likely due to limited awareness, financial constraints, and perceived inadequacies in coverage. In Maharashtra, the *kharif* season shows a robust CAGR of 19 per cent per annum, attributed to effective government initiatives and increased awareness. However, the *rabi* season's growth is only 4 per cent per annum, suggesting a need for targeted strategies to boost participation during this period. Conversely, Dharashiv faces challenges with negative CAGRs of -2 per cent per annum for *kharif* and -1 per cent per annum for *rabi*, highlighting economic hardships and distrust in insurance mechanisms. Overall, while Maharashtra shows promise, the national trend is stagnant, and Dharashiv requires urgent interventions.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of reported claim under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

The table 3. summarizes the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of reported claims in India from 2016 to 2023, The examination of the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for reported claims of insured farmers from 2016 to 2023 reveals important trends in agricultural insurance, highlighting both growth and decline across various regions and seasons. At the national level, reported claims in India show a notable increase, with a CAGR of 8 per cent per annum for the *kharif* season and an impressive 44 per cent per annum for the *rabi* season. These figures suggest a strong upward trend in the number of claims filed by insured farmers, indicating growing awareness and utilization of agricultural insurance. The significant increase during the *rabi* season may be attributed to heightened weather-related challenges or crop failures, prompting more farmers to seek compensation. This trend reflects an improving understanding among farmers of the value of insurance, which is essential for building resilience in the agricultural sector.

source: www.pmfby.gov.in.

In Maharashtra, however, the situation is concerning. The *kharif* season exhibits a dramatic decline in reported claims, with a CAGR of -41 per cent per annum. This steep drop indicates significant barriers to accessing insurance or reporting claims, which could stem from inadequate support systems or a lack of trust in the insurance process. The *rabi* season shows minimal growth at 1 per cent per annum, suggesting that while there is some improvement, it remains insufficient. The decline in claims in Maharashtra raises alarms about the effectiveness of current agricultural insurance programs and underscores the need for targeted interventions to support farmers in navigating the claims process and understanding their rights. Dharashiv presents a mixed scenario, with a CAGR of -1 per cent per annum for *kharif* and a modest increase of 4 per cent per annum for *rabi*. The negative growth in *kharif* claims points to potential underreporting or barriers that prevent farmers from accessing their insurance benefits. On the other hand, the slight increase in *rabi* claims,

while modest, may indicate growing awareness or improvements in the claims process. Nevertheless, the overall low levels of reported claims in Dharashiv suggest that more needs to be done to engage farmers and ensure they have the necessary support and information to utilize their insurance effectively.

In summary, the analysis of reported claims across different regions highlights a complex landscape of agricultural insurance utilization. While national trends show promising growth, particularly in the *rabi* season, Maharashtra and Dharashiv face significant challenges that require attention. To improve the effectiveness of agricultural insurance, stakeholders must focus on enhancing accessibility, simplifying the claims process, and increasing awareness among farmers about their insurance options.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of approved claim under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022 - 2023.

The Table 4 presented the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of approved claims in India, Maharashtra, and Dharashiv from the years 2016 to 2023. The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for reported claims in India from 2016 to 2023 reveals mixed trends in agricultural insurance. Nationally, *kharif* claims grew by 8 per cent per annum, while *rabi* claims surged by 44 per cent per annum, indicating increased awareness and utilization among farmers. The *rabi* season's growth likely reflects responses to weather challenges, highlighting the importance of insurance for resilience.

In Maharashtra, however, *kharif* claims plummeted by 41 per cent per annum, pointing to barriers in accessing insurance or a lack of trust in the process. *Rabi* claims showed minimal growth at 1 per cent per annum, signaling a need for targeted interventions to support farmers. Dharashiv exhibited a 1 per cent per annum CAGR for *kharif* and a modest 4 per cent per annum increase for *rabi*, suggesting underreporting issues and the need for improved farmer engagement. Overall, while national trends are promising, focused efforts are required to enhance accessibility, simplify claims processes, and increase farmer awareness about their insurance options.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total claim paid under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022 - 2023.

The table 5 presented illustrates the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of total claims paid in India, specifically highlighting the *kharif* and *rabi* seasons from 2016 to 2023. The analysis of the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for total claims paid in India from 2016 to 2023 reveals concerning trends in agricultural insurance. Nationally, *kharif* claims declined by 5 per cent per annum, and *rabi* claims decreased by 20 per cent per annum, indicating issues like adverse climatic conditions or reduced productivity. In Maharashtra, *kharif* claims grew by 7 per cent per annum, reflecting improved insurance awareness and crop yields, while *Rabi* claims fell significantly by 13 per cent per annum, likely due to unfavorable weather or lower outputs. Nationally, *kharif* claims declined by 5 per cent per annum, and *rabi* claims decreased by 20 per cent per annum, indicating issues like adverse climatic conditions or reduced productivity. In Maharashtra, *kharif* claims grew by 7 per cent per annum, reflecting improved insurance awareness and crop yields, while *Rabi* claims fell significantly by 13 per cent per annum, likely due to unfavorable weather or lower outputs.

Dharashiv mirrored these trends, with a slight *kharif* decline of 4 per cent per annum and a more pronounced *rabi* decrease of 9 per cent per annum, suggesting broader challenges in agricultural productivity and insurance utilization in the region. Overall, the data highlights a complex landscape of agricultural insurance, where some regions experienced growth while the national trend showed significant declines, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to address the challenges faced by farmers.

Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of total farmers benefit under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Table 6 presented the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of Total Farmers Benefit in India from 2016 to 2023. Nationally, *kharif* claims declined by 5 per cent per annum, while *rabi* claims saw a more

significant drop of 20 per cent per annum, indicating serious challenges. In Maharashtra, *kharif* claims increased by 7 per cent per annum, but *rabi* claims fell by 13 per cent per annum. Dharashiv showed a modest *kharif* decline of 4 per cent per annum and a *rabi* decrease of 9 per cent per annum, reflecting stability but no growth. Overall, these trends highlight critical issues affecting insurance claims, likely tied to climatic conditions and agricultural practices, underscoring the need for targeted interventions to support farmers.

Both analyses show a positive trend in claims paid to farmers, with Chadha and Shrivastav reporting a growth rate of 10.60 per cent per annum. However, the current data reveals mixed trends, including a national decline in claims, particularly during the *rabi* season, while Maharashtra shows positive growth. Both studies agree on increased beneficiaries, but disparities exist in growth rates. The current analysis highlights negative CAGRs for *kharif* and *rabi* claims, indicating challenges in farmer engagement, unlike Chadha and Shrivastav's overall positive metrics. Additionally, the timeframes differ, with the current study focusing on 2016-2023 and Chadha and Shrivastav on 2007-2016.

To analyze the impact of PMFBY on income stability from various crop

The analysis of insured farmers from 2016 to 2023 demonstrated the positive impact of insurance on income variability. The standard deviation of gross yield decreased from 24,445.72 without compensation to 22,798.81 with it, indicating that insurance smoothed income fluctuations and provided greater financial stability. Additionally, the mean gross yield increased from 79,254.14 without compensation to 84,776.72 with compensation, reflecting both income stabilization and an increase in average income levels. The coefficient of variation, which measures income variability relative to the mean, fell from 0.31 to 0.19, highlighting enhanced income stability. Furthermore, the income index rose from 0.69 to 0.80, indicating significant improvements in income stability due to insurance. Overall, the data shows that insurance compensation was crucial in enhancing income stability and financial outcomes for farmers, creating a more predictable financial environment.

To identify the weaknesses in implementation of PMFBY and suggest suitable measures for its improvement

Table 8. examined weaknesses in the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) based on feedback from 120 insured farmers. The most significant constraint was the delay in insurance claim payments, which received a mean score of 73.92, ranking first at 51.33%. This delay critically affects farmers' recovery from crop losses and undermines trust in the system, highlighting the need for streamlined claims processing. Low awareness of PMFBY ranked second with a mean score of 70.09, indicating a lack of information about the scheme's benefits.

The third issue was the shortage of well-trained insurance professionals, scoring 66.37, which hampers farmers' ability to navigate claims effectively. Other concerns included improper reporting of crop losses (58.68), technological challenges during enrollment (50.93), and insufficient coordination between banks and farmers (49.93). Comparative analysis with Pradhan *et al.* (2021) revealed similar constraints but highlighted different operational challenges. Both studies stress the need for targeted interventions to improve PMFBY's effectiveness and rebuild farmers' trust through enhanced communication and education.

Suggestions given by sampled Insured farmers

The table 9. presented highlights suggestions from 120 insured farmers to enhance the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). The top recommendation was for quicker claim settlements, with 118 farmers (98.33%) emphasizing the need for timely payments to reduce financial stress after crop losses. Transparency in the claims process was the second priority, receiving 113 responses (94.17%), as farmers sought clearer communication to minimize misunderstandings. The third suggestion involved increasing compensation rates, supported by 75 farmers (62.50%), to better address crop failure losses. Additionally,

farmers advocated for a local public grievance settlement mechanism (74 responses, 61.67%) to resolve concerns efficiently. Other notable suggestions included local language documentation (73 responses, 60.83%) to improve accessibility and awareness programs (17 responses, 14.17%) to boost understanding of PMFBY. Overall, there was a clear consensus on the need for timely compensation, transparency, and effective grievance mechanisms to enhance PMFBY's effectiveness and farmer acceptance.

Conclusion

The analysis of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) reveals significant insights into the challenges and progress of agricultural insurance in India, particularly in Maharashtra and Dharashiv. The data from 2016 to 2023 indicates a troubling stagnation in the growth of insured farmers and areas, coupled with disparities in claim reports and overall utilization of insurance products. While the national trend reflects some promise in claim reporting especially during the *rabi* season the *kharif* season shows alarming declines in Maharashtra, underscoring barriers that farmers face in accessing and effectively utilizing insurance.

Particularly in Dharashiv, the minimal growth rates, coupled with negative trends in claim reporting, highlight systemic issues such as low awareness and economic hardships that deter farmers from participating in the scheme. The findings underscore the necessity for targeted interventions to enhance accessibility and trust in the PMFBY, ensuring that farmers can navigate the claims process more effectively. The significant delays in claim settlements, coupled with inadequate outreach and training, point to a critical need for operational improvements within the program.

Farmers' feedback emphasizes the urgent requirement for streamlined claims processes and increased transparency. Their suggestions for quicker settlements, higher compensation rates, and local grievance mechanisms reflect a desire for a more responsive and supportive insurance framework. Overall, enhancing the PMFBY's effectiveness hinges on addressing these weaknesses and fostering a better understanding among farmers about their rights and the benefits of the program. By doing so, it will be possible to build resilience within the agricultural sector, ultimately leading to improved financial stability for farmers across India.

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Table 1: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Insured farmers under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-7**	-2**
		t value	-1.98	-0.62
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	20	3**
		t value	2.98	0.25
3	Dharashiv	CAGR	1%**	1%**
		t value	-0.14	1.02

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Area Insured under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	1%**	1%**
		t value	0.51	0.34
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	19%**	4%**
		t value	1.34	0.29
3	Dharashiv	CAGR	-2%**	-1%**
		t value	-0.55	-0.44

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36).

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Reported claim under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	8%	44**
		t value	2.41	1.75
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-41**	1**
		t value	-1.52	0.04
3	Dharashiv	CAGR	-1%**	4%**
		t value	0.28	0.35

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Approved claim under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022 - 2023.

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-60%**	-26%**
		t value	-2.47	-0.84
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	-42%**	3%**
		t value	-1.57	0.11
3	Dharashiv	CAGR	8%**	3%**
		t value	1.7	1.2

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36)

source: www.pmfby.gov.in.

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total Claim under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-5%**	-20%**
		t value	-1.01	-2.35
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	7%**	-13%**
		t value	0.83	-0.55
3	Dharashiv	CAGR	-4%**	-9%**
		t value	-0.17	-0.71

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36)

source: www.pmfby.gov.in.

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of Total Farmers Benefit under PMFBY for the period 2016-2017 to 2022- 2023.

Sl. No.	Regions	Particulars	Kharif	Rabi
1	India	CAGR	-6%**	-19%**
		t value	-3.02	-2.41
2	Maharashtra	CAGR	1%**	-19%**
		t value	0.11	-0.73

3	Dharashiv	CAGR	-4%**	-3%**
		t value	-0.17	-0.24

Note: ** Significant at (5%) level, t Table value (2.36)

source: www.pmfby.gov.in.

Table 7: Gross income stability and income index of sampled Insured farmers from year 2016-2023

Particular	Gross yield without compensation (r)	Gross yield with compensation (r)
Standard Deviation	24445.72	22798.81
Mean	79254.14	84776.72
Coefficient of Covariation	0.31	0.19
Income Index	0.69	0.80

Table 8: Weakness in implementation of PMFBY

Sl. no.	Constraints	Mean score	Rank	Percentage
1	Delay payment of insurance claims.	73.92	1	51.33
2	Low awareness about PMFBY.	70.09	2	48.67
3	Lack of well-trained insurance professionals	66.37	3	46.09
4	Problem of improper reporting in case of crop loss	58.68	4	40.75
5	Problems with the technology used for enrolment	50.93	5	35.37
6	Lack of education of farmers.	31.78	8	22.07
7	Expert unavailable for assessment of crop	39.96	7	27.75
8	Insufficient Co-ordination of Banks and Farmers	49.93	6	34.67
9	Negative attitude of farmers towards this scheme	26.87	9	18.66
10	Inadequate support and responsiveness from insurance providers	20.31	10	14.10

Table 9: Suggestion of crop insured farmers for improvement of PMFBY

Sl. No.	Suggestion	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Public-grievance settlement mechanism at local level.	74	61.67	4
2	Quick settlement of claims.	118	98.33	1
3	Need for transparency in settlement of claims.	113	94.17	2
4	Local language documentation	73	60.83	5
5	Increase the Compensation Under PMFBY	75	62.50	3
6	Awareness programmes for farmer regarding PMFBY must be organized.	17	14.17	7
7	Inform farmers before deducting premium.	9	7.50	8
8	Farmers may be trained for e-filing of insurance	7	5.83	10
9	Crop insurance should be open for those who practices farming, not for land owners	56	46.67	6